

IGWE-EBI VIVIAN

REPORT ON THE UNITED NATION'S RESPONSE TO THE OUTBREAK OF EBOLA IN SIERRA LEONE FROM 2014 TO 2016

TABLE OF CONTENTS

A. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

B. INTRODUCTION

1. HUMANITARIANISM

1.1 DEFINITION OF HUMANITARIANISM

1.2 UN AND HUMANITARIANISM

1.3 PRINCIPLES OF HUMANITARIANISM

1.3.1 HUMANITY

1.3.2 IMPARTIALITY

1.3.3 NEUTRALITY

1.3.4 OPERATIONAL INDEPENDENCE

1.4 THE SPHERE PROJECT

2. UNITED NATIONS RESPONSE TO COMMUNICABLE DISEASE OUTBREAK

2.1 UN HUMANITARIAN ACTORS

2.1.1 WHO

2.1.2 UNOCHA

2.1.3 UNICEF

2.1.4 UNDP

3. EBOLA OUTBREAK IN SIERRA LEONE

3.1 EBOLA VIRUS DISEASE

3.2 EBOLA VIRUS DISEASE OUTBREAK IN SIERRA LEONE

3.3 UN RESPONSE TO THE OUTBREAK IN SIERRA LEONE

3.3.1 WHO

3.3.2 UNICEF

3.3.3 UNDP

3.3.4 UNMEER

3.3.5 UN EBOLA RESPONSE MPTF

3.4 CHALLENGES IN THE UN RESPONSE

3.5 OUTCOME OF THE RESPONSE

4. EVALUATION OF THE UN RESPONSE

4.1 COMPLIANCE TO HUMANITARIAN PRINCIPLES

4.2 COMPLIANCE TO THE SPHERE PROJECT STANDARDS

4.3 LESSONS LEARNED IN THE RESPONSE

5. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

5.1 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVED RESPONSE

5.2 CONCLUSION

6. REFERENCES

A. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Sierra Leone experienced a severe Ebola outbreak from 2014 to 2016, resulting in over 3,500 deaths and significant economic and healthcare damage (CDC, 2023). In response to this catastrophe, the United Nations mobilised a wide variety of UN organisations and allies. Through a critical analysis of humanitarianism, its principles, UN's role in humanitarian aid, and the existing structure for responding to health emergencies like communicable disease outbreaks, this report seeks to provide a thorough analysis of the UN's humanitarian response to the outbreak of Ebola Virus Disease in Sierra Leone. It examines the strategies, challenges, and outcomes of the UN's efforts to contain the outbreak. This report also evaluates these efforts considering the standards and principles guiding humanitarian interventions and posits that the UN humanitarian intervention in the Sierra Leone EVD outbreak aligned with the principles of humanitarianism to a large extent, but failed to comply with the Sphere project standards. The UN and other humanitarian actors are also urged to improve their responses to outbreaks of communicable diseases. Other key objectives of this report are to gain a better

understanding of the UN's response to major global health crisis, and to extract valuable lessons that might be applied to future operations in humanitarianism.

B. INTRODUCTION

This report begins by outlining the definitions and ideals of humanitarianism, then moves on to the UN's strategy to contain communicable disease epidemics, including the partners and techniques employed. It then analyses and evaluates the UN's reaction to the Ebola Virus disease outbreak in Sierra Leone between 2014 and 2016, focusing on humanitarian principles and standards. Finally, the paper finishes with recommendations based on the offered findings.

1. HUMANITARIANISM

1.1 DEFINITION

At its core, humanitarianism believes in every human's worth and dignity, committing to promoting and safeguarding their welfare and rights, especially during crisis. This includes a variety of actions targeted at meeting the needs of disadvantaged groups, such as those impacted by natural catastrophes, armed conflict, or persistent poverty. As a result, humanitarianism is a vital component of international efforts to improve equity and human welfare and is essential to sustaining the core values of human dignity and equality. As defined by the UN (2023), humanitarianism are actions that improve the well-being of humans. especially in dire situations like war and conflict, natural disasters and extreme poverty. Slim (2002) states that humanitarianism is a moral principle embracing the belief that humans have value for themselves, such that everyone's suffering is of equal importance.

1.2. UNITED NATIONS AND HUMANITARIANISM:

The bedrock of humanitarian endeavors lies in the fundamental principles of humanity, impartiality, neutrality, and independence (UNCHR, 2023). These guiding tenets, which have their roots in international humanitarian law, have been formally embraced by the United Nations through General Assembly Resolutions 46/182 and 58/114, attesting to their universal acceptance and applicability (ICRC, 2023). The Code of Conduct for the International Red Cross and Red Crescent Movement and Non-Governmental Organizations in Disaster Relief and the Core Humanitarian Standard on Quality and Accountability serve as benchmarks for humanitarian actors worldwide (IFRC, 2023). These principles and standards form a crucial framework for ensuring ethical and moral standards guide humanitarian efforts, driven solely by the needs and interests of those being served (Weiss, 1999). The UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (UNOCHA) is tasked with the coordination of humanitarian actors' participation in responses to humanitarian crisis. (UNOCHA, 2023).

1.3 PRINCIPLES OF HUMANITARIANISM

1.3.1 HUMANITY: The basic motivation for humanitarian action is to alleviate hardship and save lives, with a strong emphasis on protecting and restoring individual dignity. In this aspect, humanity acts as the driving force behind any reaction to a crisis.

1.3.2 IMPARTIALITY: Humanitarian actors set themselves apart from other crisis responses by adhering to the idea of impartiality. This means that humanitarian action is only motivated by need, with priority given to the most urgent cases regardless of race, country, gender, religious or political affiliation, or social status.

1.3.3 NEUTRALITY: The neutrality of humanitarian action is further reinforced when humanitarian actors refrain from taking sides in hostilities or engaging in political, racial, religious, or ideological disputes.

1.3.4 OPERATIONAL INDEPENDENCE: Independence is a critical characteristic of humanitarian action, requiring that humanitarian organisations maintain a level of autonomy and are not subject to control or influence by external entities.

1.4 THE SPHERE PROJECT

The Sphere Project was launched in 1997 by NGOs and the International Red Cross and Red Crescent Movement to establish minimum standards for humanitarian response (ICRC, 2023) based on human rights and humanitarian law (IFRC, 2023). It has become a widely recognized and respected standard, providing guidelines for humanitarian assistance in disaster and conflict settings (Sphere Project, 2018). The Sphere Handbook outlines technical guidelines and minimum standards for key sectors of humanitarian response, including water supply, sanitation, hygiene promotion, food security and nutrition, shelter, settlement, non-food items, and health (Sphere Association, 2018). These standards are developed through a consultative process involving a range of stakeholders, including affected communities, and are regularly updated to reflect changes in best practice and new challenges (Salama et al., 2001). The Sphere standards also serve as a tool for monitoring and evaluating humanitarian responses, enhancing the quality and accountability of humanitarian assistance.

2. UN'S RESPONSE TO COMMUNICABLE DISEASES.

2.1 UN HUMANITARIAN ACTORS:

The United Nations plays a critical role in responding to communicable diseases' outbreaks worldwide. The response of the UN is led by the World Health Organization (WHO), which is the specialized UN agency responsible for global public health (UN, 2023). UNICEF and the UNDP also play key roles in supporting the UN response to the outbreak of communicable diseases (UN, 2023). The UN's global recognition and commitment to the four principles of humanitarianism underscore its efforts to respond to communicable disease outbreaks. Its approach to epidemics is focused mainly on prevention, detection, and control.

2.1.1 WORLD HEALTH ORGANISATION

The WHO is responsible for leading and coordinating international response efforts, primarily focusing on identifying the virus or bacteria causing the outbreak, disease surveillance, case management, contact tracing, and infection prevention and control (WHO, 2023). WHO holds responsibility for providing guidance to governments in affected countries as the UN's lead agency for global health crisis; as well as working with the country's health authorities, and other humanitarian actors to ensure an efficient and effective response.

2.1.2 UN OFFICE FOR THE COORDINATION OF HUMANITARIAN AFFAIRS (UNOCHA)

UNOCHA is in charge of bringing together humanitarian actors to ensure a harmonised and efficient response to communicable diseases' outbreaks. UNOCHA ensures that each actor can contribute to the collective response effort within an established framework. (UN, 2023). The UN's systemic response to outbreaks of communicable diseases reiterates its commitment to protecting the health and well-being of people worldwide.

2.1.3 UNITED NATIONS CHILDREN'S FUND

UNICEF plays a critical role in containing communicable diseases' outbreaks, especially in protecting children and other vulnerable persons. In epidemics, UNICEF works closely with other UN agencies, governments, and partners to deliver crucial interventions. UNICEF provides life-saving aids such as treatments and vaccinations, it also supports healthcare systems in implementing adequate response to outbreaks (UNICEF, 2023).

2.1.4 UNITED NATIONS DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME

UNDP also provides support to countries affected by communicable disease epidemics by strengthening existing healthcare systems, providing access to health technologies and to medicines, and supporting the enactment of policies and strategies for disease prevention and control.

Now that a brief overview on the main humanitarian actors and their coordination efforts have been provided, an overview on the Ebola crisis is provided prior to an evaluation on the role and coordination of humanitarian actors in the field.

3. EBOLA OUTBREAK IN SIERRA LEONE

3.1 EBOLA VIRUS DISEASE

Ebola virus disease (EVD) is a life-threatening, transmissible disease that typically affects primates: non-human and human alike. Contact with contaminated person's body fluid or surface spreads the virus within the human population. (WHO, 2021). The first known outbreak caused by two distinct viruses: Zaire ebolavirus and Sudan ebolavirus occurred in 1976 in the Democratic Republic of Congo and South Sudan (CDC 2021). In 2014, EVD outbreak in West African quickly spread across borders, becoming the largest and most complex Ebola outbreak to history (WHO, 2021). Most of the transmission occurred among family members, with direct contact with the bodies of those who died proving most hazardous (CDC 2021). The outbreak eventually infected over 28,000 people and killed over 11,000 (WHO, 2021).

3.2 EBOLA VIRUS DISEASE OUTBREAK IN SIERRA LEONE

With 14,124 confirmed cases and 3,956 deaths reported by the WHO as of 8 March 2016, Sierra Leone was the most severely affected country. Several factors aided the spread of EVD in Sierra Leone, including weak health systems, poor infrastructure, a lack of public health education, and cultural practices related to caregiving and burial that resulted in the handling of Ebola victims' corpses, putting individuals at high risk of infection. The virus quickly spread throughout the country and the capital city of Freetown was the most heavily affected.

3.3 UN'S RESPONSE TO THE OUTBREAK IN SIERRA LEONE

In reaction to the epidemic, the UN undertook a huge, coordinated effort to prevent and contain the virus's spread. Co-ordinated by UNOCHA, UN mobilized the different agencies to the different UN agencies to tackle the multi-faceted challenges that outbreak posed (Kucharski et al., 2015). In addition to WHO, UNOCHA, UNICEF and UNDP, the UN established the United Nations Mission for Ebola Emergency Response (UNMEER). It also established Ebola Response Multi-Partner Trust Fund (Elston et al., 2016). Each of these humanitarian actors were fundamental in containing the outbreak in Sierra Leone from 2014 to 2016. Their roles are explained in the following sub-sections.

3.3.1 WHO:

The World Health Organisation (WHO) was critical in containing the EVD outbreak in Sierra Leone by delivering technical assistance to the government and managing worldwide responses through the Global Outbreak Alert and Response Network. A multi-pronged approach was adopted by the organisation some of which included: infection prevention and control, case management, vaccination, community engagement, and contact tracing. It supported the establishment of Ebola Treatment Centers (ETCs) and Community Care Centers (CCCs) to cater to infected persons. (WHO, 2016). It also provided technical guidance on infection prevention and control measures, deployed mobile laboratory teams, and helped develop and implement vaccination campaigns. Moreover, it partnered with other UN agencies and NGOs to ensure a harmonised response, it also funding from several countries, including the US, UK, and EU.

3.3.2 UNICEF

UNICEF played a key role in the response to the Ebola virus outbreak in Sierra Leone by focusing on four key areas: community mobilization, infection prevention and control, social protection, and child protection (Pronyk, 2016). UNICEF worked with local leaders to raise awareness and establish community task forces to disseminate accurate information. Infection prevention and control efforts included supporting the government in setting up ETCs and CCCs, providing supplies and training, and deploying mobile laboratory teams. Social protection involved providing cash transfers and psychosocial support to vulnerable households, supporting safe burial practices, and promoting the reopening of schools. Additionally, UNICEF's child protection interventions provided critical support to affected children through psychosocial support, child-friendly spaces, and promoting child protection policies.

3.3.3 UNDP

The UNDP's role was key in containing the Ebola outbreak in Sierra Leone. UNDP worked closely with the government and other actors to address the outbreak and mitigate its impact on the country's socio-economic development (Davis, 2015). A key area of UNDP's response was the restoration of basic social services, such as the construction and rehabilitation of health facilities and schools in affected areas. UNDP also aided with the provision of medical supplies and equipment, including ambulances. It supported the government to develop social-protection policies and programs to support vulnerable groups; develop a recovery plan to guide the country's socioeconomic recovery; and develop national preparedness and response plan to guide future responses to potential outbreaks.

3.3.4 UNMEER

The United Nations Mission for Ebola Emergency Response (UNMEER) was established in 2014 to oversee the intervention efforts to the Ebola epidemic. In Sierra Leone, UNMEER focused on three core areas: providing operational support to the national response, coordinating international assistance, and facilitating effective communication and information management (UN, 2023). UNMEER collaborated with the government of Sierra Leone to build a comprehensive monitoring system, and provided training and logistic support to healthcare personnel on Ebola treatment and preventative measures, in order to contain the spread. UNMEER also facilitated the sharing of real-time information among partners, enabling a coordinated response to the outbreak.

3.3.5 EBOLA RESPONSE MULTI-PARTNER TRUST FUND (MPTF).

The UN established the Ebola Response Multi-Partner Trust Fund as a coordinated mechanism to support the response to the outbreak. The fund was established to provide a coordinated channel for donors to help the UN's response to the outbreak (UNMPTF, 2014). It provided essential resources for the deployment of health workers, provision of medical supplies and equipment, and establishment of ETCs and CCCs. Additionally, the fund supported the deployment of mobile laboratory teams and training of community health workers to promote community engagement and accurate information dissemination. It also funded the National Ebola Response Centre, which oversaw the whole response in Sierra Leone.

3.4 CHALLENGES IN THE UN RESPONSE

Given the country's poor health system and limited resources, the UN's intervention in the Sierra Leone outbreak had some challenges. Some of such challenges included: delayed recognition of the outbreak's severity hindered the mobilization of resources to prevent the disease's spread. In addition, the country's weak healthcare system lacked the necessary personnel, supplies and infrastructure to handle the outbreak (WHO, 2014). Traditional funeral practices and mistrust of international aid workers also presented challenges.

3.5 OUTCOME OF THE RESPONSE

The UN's response to the Ebola outbreak in Sierra Leone was significant in mitigating the spread of EVD and saving lives. To contain the outbreak, the UN agencies, worked closely with the Sierra Leone government and other partners to employ a variety of strategies, including community involvement, infection prevention and control, child protection, and social protection. The United Nations' involvement in the outbreak led to considerable decrease in the number of new Ebola cases in Sierra Leone. By January 2016, there were no new cases, and the country was declared Ebola-free in March 2016 (WHO, 2016). The UN's efforts were significant in the prevention of the outbreak from spreading beyond Sierra Leone's borders and becoming a pandemic.

4. EVALUATION OF THE UN RESPONSE

4.1 COMPLIANCE TO HUMANITARIAN PRINCIPLES

The UN response to the Ebola outbreak in Sierra Leone is significantly reflective of the four core principles of humanitarianism, namely humanity, neutrality, impartiality, and independence. Firstly, the principle of humanity is evident in the UN's response as it prioritized the welfare of the affected population, recognizing the severity of the outbreak and the urgent need to prevent its spread. Secondly, the principle of neutrality was upheld as the UN maintained a non-partisan approach to delivering aid and support to all affected communities, without taking sides in the conflict or politics of the region. Thirdly, the UN's efforts to provide equitable support and aid to all those impacted, regardless of religion, nationality or race, exhibited the concept of impartiality. This was evident in the allocation of resources, which prioritized areas with the highest incidence of the disease, without discrimination or favoritism towards any group. Finally, the principle of operational independence was upheld as the UN's intervention was driven by the needs of the affected population rather than the interests of any government or organisation. The UN maintained its independence and acted in the best interests of the affected communities, despite working closely with Sierra Leone's government. The UN provided impartial and independent assistance, based on its own assessment of the needs on the ground, without external influence or pressure.

4.2 COMPLIANCE TO THE SPHERE PROJECT STANDARDS

The UN's response to the Ebola outbreak in Sierra Leone did not align with the minimum standards set by Sphere Project, which covers critical areas in humanitarian response, including water supply and sanitation, food security, shelter, and health services. Specifically, the UN response failed to meet the Sphere standards for safe water and sanitation facilities, which presented a significant challenge to containing the outbreak. Poor sanitation and hygiene practices increased the risk of transmission, while the lack of safe water undermined prevention efforts. Additionally, the UN's healthcare provision fell short of Sphere standards, despite attempts to establish Ebola treatment centers. There were insufficient beds and employees to address patient needs, and the facilities lacked basic supplies, equipment, and infection control procedures, putting both patients and healthcare workers' safety at risk.

4.3 LESSONS LEARNED IN THE RESPONSE

The outbreak of EVD in Sierra Leone took a toll on Sierra Leone's economy, and it presently relies heavily on aid (Adam Smith International, 2023). The UN's response to the Ebola outbreak in Sierra Leone yielded several lessons learned. One key lesson is the importance of early recognition and rapid response to contain the outbreak. Recognizing the severity of the outbreak in Sierra Leone and mobilizing resources accordingly was essential to prevent the disease from spreading quickly and widely. Effective and transparent communication with affected communities was also a crucial factor in gaining their trust and support for the response efforts. Community engagement and involvement in the response are also recognized as crucial, as community members play a crucial role in identifying cases and implementing prevention measures. (Anderson and Woodrow, 2006) Another lesson learnt is that more coordination and collaboration among the different actors participating in the response, including as international organisations, national governments, and local stakeholders, is required (UNOCHA, 2015). This includes the coordination of resources, data sharing, and effective communication to ensure that response efforts are complementary and avoid duplication. The importance of investing in healthcare systems and infrastructure in vulnerable countries is also underscored, as Sierra Leone's weak healthcare system exacerbated the impact of the outbreak. This includes building capacity in areas such as laboratory testing, disease surveillance, and infection control measures.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

5.1 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPROVED HUMANITARIAN RESPONSE

-Prioritize community engagement and work closely with local leaders to build trust and ensure that communities are actively involved in the response (SCHR, 2023). This includes involving communities in decision-making processes and adapting response strategies to fit the local context.

-Collaborate with governments to strengthen healthcare systems in afflicted countries. This includes expanding the number of healthcare personnel, strengthening infrastructure, and ensuring appropriate supplies and equipment are available (UNDP, 2015).

-Increase cross-border collaboration and coordination to avoid disease spread across borders. This involves cross-national sharing of information, resources, and best practises.

-Improve collection of data and its analysis to track disease transmission and improve response implementation. This entails improving surveillance systems, establishing early warning systems, and assessing data as soon as possible to identify and contain epidemics.

-Ensure that their actions follow standards of humanitarian aid like those described in the Sphere Project. This includes ensuring that safe water and sanitation facilities are available, providing adequate healthcare services, and prioritizing the protection of vulnerable populations.

-Continue to work with the Sierra Leone and other governments in Africa to strengthen the continent's healthcare system and improve its capacity to respond to future outbreaks.

5.2 CONCLUSION

The 2014 Ebola epidemic in Sierra Leone highlighted the limitations of addressing outbreaks of communicable diseases in poor countries. The outbreak had significant social and economic consequences, and the response involved a range of UN Humanitarian actors working together to contain the disease and mitigate its impact. The outbreak highlighted the country's health-care system's flaws and emphasised the necessity for a cohesive and effective response. The lessons learned from the outbreak have led to improvements in preparedness and response to future outbreaks, including the COVID-19 pandemic.

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